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Slag Valorisation Symposium

Science, Innovation & Entrepreneurship
in Pursuit of a Sustainable World

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Editors

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KU LEUVEN

MATERIALS ENGINEERING

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PREFACE

Aims and scope

We are grateful for your interest in this assembly of slag valorising research, and we proudly present you this book of proceedings. The 6th edition of the International Slag Valorisation Symposium finds itself in a time of commotion about climate change. While the youth is demonstrating to demand action from policymakers to prevent further global warming, conservatives are struggling to keep the denial of the urgency of reducing CO₂ emissions alive. In these times it is necessary to look at the valorisation of slags from a broader perspective than the search for a solution for a specific industrial by-product. Slag valorisation is a way to decrease the CO₂ footprint of nowadays' society. Taking a slag as a resource, for the recovery of metals or the use as a binder in concrete, can increase the sustainability of production with respect to conventional processing routes. The realisation of this extra dimension imposes a self-assessment and reflection on the processes we propose as a sustainable alternative. This 2019 edition is subtitled "Science, Innovation & Entrepreneurship in Pursuit of a Sustainable World", acknowledging the need for bravery and entrepreneurial actions if we want to aim for sustainable development.

Programme

The 6th International Slag Valorisation Symposium is composed of 10 thematic sessions, covering the entire slag production and treatment chain:

- Slag valorisation and thermodynamics
- Alternative cements and aggregates
- Slag properties at high temperature
- Slag storage conditioning and leaching
- Metal recovery
- Slag valorisation as ceramics and insulation materials
- Innovation, business models and case studies
- Metal recovery and internal use of slags
- Alternative heating, cooling and reactivity
- Alkali-activation

Besides the oral and poster presentations and the exhibition during the three Symposium days (2-4 April 2019), we hope the participants will enjoy the preceding workshops on carbonation technology or inorganic polymer technology for residue valorisation (1 April 2019) as well as the post-symposium plant visit to Metallo or Orbix (5 April 2019).

Venue

The 6th edition of this conference for the first time goes outside of the city borders of Leuven, to Mechelen, in search of accommodation with more grandeur. Mechelen is a typical Belgian/Flemish city, known for its centre with remainders of the medieval and renaissance ages. In the neighbourhood of the main market square “Grote Markt” you can find the St. Rumbold’s cathedral and city hall, while going a bit further down the small streets, you will see treats like the Court of Busleyden. We hope you will enjoy the city as well as the conference.

Dr. Ir. Annelies Malfiet, Dr. Ir. Arne Pyes, Dr. Ir. Andrea Di Maria

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For the 6th time now, we have enjoyed organising the International Slag Valorisation Symposium. But this would not have been possible without the help of a multitude of people. The Organising Team would, therefore, like to thank everyone who contributed to the realisation of this event, thereby bringing together about 200 specialists from all over the world.

We want to start with acknowledging all participants for their contribution to the field of slag valorisation through their presence, their presentations and posters, and their discussions and interactions during the Symposium. Their abstracts and papers were carefully reviewed by the Scientific Committee, with support from our internal reviewers, for which we greatly appreciate their valuable input to help us create an inspiring and qualitative program. We are also grateful to the invited speakers for accepting our invitation to give a plenary lecture and share their expertise in the field of slag valorisation. Finally, the Chairpersons are acknowledged for their professional guidance of the different Symposium sessions.

The organisation of this Symposium would not have been possible without additional financial support next to the registration fees and the contribution from EIT RawMaterials. We therefore thank our sponsors ArcelorMittal, Imerys, InsPyro, Aperam, Umicore, Orbix and Metallo, together with our exhibitors, Imerys, InsPyro, Metallo, Orbix, and ResourceFull. We also thank SIM² KU Leuven & the Centre for Resource Recovery and Recycling (CR³) for their support.

A special word of thanks goes to the conference coordinators An Serbruyns (madebyan) and Amaury Dewilde (Go Figure) for the precious planning and organisation of the Symposium, for all communications, for the Symposium website and proceedings and many more. Finally, we are grateful to all people from the Department of Materials Engineering for their support in organising this Symposium.

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RECOVERING CHROMIUM FROM STAINLESS STEEL AND FERROCHROME SLAGS

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Introduction

Currently, about 75% of the chromium is being imported into the EU.¹ In the value chain of stainless steel production, significant amounts of chromium (Cr) are lost in ferrochromium (FeCr) slags and stainless steel (SS) slags. FeCr slags are generated during the production of FeCr, an intermediate product for SS production (1.1-1.6 ton slag/ton high carbon (HC) FeCr;² 2.4-2.5 ton slag/low carbon (LC) FeCr). In 2014 the global FeCr production amounted to 11.7 Mt.³ SS slag is a by-product generated during the production of SS, at approximately one ton of slag per 3 tons of produced SS. The global stainless steel production was 38 Mt in 2013.⁴ Cr concentrations in FeCr and SS slags are in the range of 2-8% and 1-2%, respectively. Johnson *et al.* has estimated that in 2000 in Europe (including Turkey) 74 900 t/y and 18 700 t/y Cr was lost in FeCr slag and SS slag, respectively.⁵ In both materials, Cr is present within entrapped metallic particles (Fe-Cr alloys) and/or as stable spinels. To unlock the potential of these low-grade resources, a radically new approach to metal recovery must be deployed. The aim of the presented work is to develop a process for recovering Cr from SS and FeCr slags based on the smart integration of enhanced pretreatment and selective alkaline leaching or alkaline roasting followed by water leaching.

Experimental

Materials

Four different Cr-containing slags (listed in Table 1) were investigated in this study.

Table 1: Samples investigated in this study

Slag sample	Sample description	Cr [%]	Mineralogical form of Cr in the sample
CS EAF	Carbon steel EAF slag	2.6	Mg-Cr spinel (MgCr_2O_4)
LC FeCr	Slag from LC FeCr production	3.2	Mg-Cr spinel (MgCr_2O_4); FeCr
HC FeCr	Slag from HC FeCr production	11.5	Mg-Cr spinel (MgCr_2O_4); FeCr
SS	Stainless steel slag	2.5	Mg-Cr spinel (MgCr_2O_4)

Methods

Physical separation

Magnetic and density separation techniques (listed in Table 2) were applied for selected slag samples. All magnetic separation equipment was produced by Master Magnets Ltd. The wet shaking table used in this test was built by Holman-Wilfley Ltd.

Table 2: Physical separation techniques used in this study

Separation technique	Description (Type)	Basic parameters	Material tested
LIMS	Dry low intensity magnetic separation (Handheld ferrite magnet)	0.15 T magnetic field	HC FeCr
HIMS	Dry high intensity magnetic separation (Handheld RARE magnet)	1 T magnetic field	LC FeCr HC FeCr
WLIMS	Wet low intensity magnetic separation (Wetchute with ferrite magnet)	0.1 T magnetic field	HC FeCr
WHIMS	Wet high intensity magnetic separation (Wetchute with RARE magnet)	1 T magnetic field	SS HC FeCr
WHIMSe	Wet high gradient/intensity magnetic separation (WHIMS 500)	0-2 T magnetic field	SS LC FeCr
WST	Wet shaking table - density separation (Type 800)	stroke speed = 250 rpm washing water = 1000 L/h feed water = 250 L/h	HC FeCr

Microwave (MW) assisted leaching

Microwave assisted leaching and roasting were performed in MW equipment (*Milestone Flexiwave* and *Pyrowave*, respectively) shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: MW equipment used for MW assisted leaching (left) and MW roasting (right)

During MW assisted leaching 9 g of CS EAF slag was mixed with 15 mL NaOCl (15%) and selected amounts of NaOH (0.2-1.6 g). Conditions of the MW leaching are listed in Table 3. After MW leaching additional 90 mL of distilled water was added and the mixture was shaken for 60 min at 25°C. After filtration, leachates were analysed by ICP-OES (Avio 500, PerkinElmer).

MW roasting followed by water leaching

Samples consisting of a mixture of 3 g of SS slag, an alkali salt (NaOH) and an oxidant (NaNO₃) were roasted at conditions listed in Table 3. After MW roasting, the samples were leached in distilled water at 25°C, L/S = 10 for 60 min.

Table 3: Experimental conditions of MW assisted leaching and roasting

Parameter	MW leaching	MW roasting
Max. power used[W]	1000	1000
Time [min]	60 and 120	30
Temperature [°C]	105	400
Material tested	CS EAF slag	SS slag

Results and discussion

Physical separation

Results of physical separation tests (Table 4) show the potential of magnetic and density separation to concentrate Cr from Cr-containing slags.

Table 4: Summary of the results after physical separation

Slag sample	Techniques used	Initial Cr content (wt%)	Cr content after separation (wt%)	Yield (wt%)	Cr recovery (wt%)
LC FeCr	WHIMSe	3.2	7.3	13	25
HC FeCr	LIMS	11.5	27.6	20	50
SS	WHIMS	2.5	8.8	7	31
HC FeCr	WST	10.1	32.8	12	46

*WST was performed only for fraction 1-2 mm

In the case of CS EAF slag, LIMS was performed with the aim to recover steel particles which could be returned directly to the steelmaking process. The yield of the steel particles was 25 wt%.

MW assisted leaching

As seen from Figure 2, 44% of Cr can be extracted from CS EAF slag by applying alkaline MW assisted leaching. It is evident that the amount of NaOH is an important parameter affecting Cr extraction. The dissolution of matrix elements (Fe, Si, Ca, Mg and Al) was below 1%.

MW roasting follow by water leaching

Results of MW roasting followed by water leaching for the SS slag material are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Results of MW assisted leaching (CS EAF slag)

Figure 3: Results of MW roasting followed by water leaching (SS slag)

More than 90% of Cr can be selectively extracted from SS slag by alkali roasting at 400°C at a weight ratio NaOH:slag of 2:3 followed by water leaching in the presence of NaNO₃ as oxidant.

Conclusion

Physical separation tests concentrated Cr significantly by using magnetic and density separation, whereby Cr contents can be increased by a factor of 3. More than 90% of Cr can be selectively leached out from SS slag by a combination of alkali microwave roasting and water leaching.

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